

**EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF ROTOR-STATOR INTERACTIONS ACROSS
ALL AXIAL GAPS OF A 2.5-STAGE AXIAL COMPRESSOR FOR IMPROVED
FORCED RESPONSE PREDICTION**

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ABSTRACT

In this article results of azimuthal mode analysis in six axial planes between, upstream and downstream of the blade rows of a 2.5-stage axial compressor are presented. In addition, sources of experimental measurement uncertainty are pointed out and discussed.

Experimental results show a wide range of dominant frequencies with high pressure fluctuation amplitudes in the inter-row sections, including frequencies that arise from a single rotor and those that result from an interaction of both rotors. These frequencies from rotor interactions are also a potential source of blade excitation in the context of forced response. Experimental evidence confirms that these interaction frequencies, with amplitudes up to the same order of magnitude as the ones of single rotor origin, are present.

An azimuthal mode analysis was performed for three different operating points at all six measuring planes with wall flush mounted sensors at the casing. It was found that most dominant modes tend to propagate mainly downstream, while only few do so upstream. For those operating points under consideration, numerical simulations are also in agreement with this observation. Up to a point where measurement uncertainties prohibit further comparison to numerical results, a qualitative agreement of azimuthal mode amplitudes over the axial measuring planes between simulation and experiment could be observed.

For the experimental measurements, several sensors were used per plane, which were all evaluated independently. Results

show differing azimuthal mode amplitudes where, within measurement uncertainty, the same were expected. An additional seventh axial plane behind stator 2 was used to examine these differences in further detail.

Keywords: Experimental Azimuthal Mode Analysis, Axial Compressor, Uncertainty Analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

Forced blade vibrations can result in high costs if large blade deflections or stresses are not found in an early design phase. To avoid cost-intensive design changes at a late stage of development, accurate numerical prediction of aeroelastic phenomena is necessary.

In recent years, several authors have studied the impact of acoustic modes (Tyler-Sofrin-Modes [1]) on blade vibration excitation. Schoenenborn and Ashcroft [2], for example, compared different numerical methods to carry out aeroelastic analyses of an axial compressor. At low rotational speed, both a linearized and a nonlinear solver, revealed similar results for aerodynamic work and pressure amplitudes on the blade surfaces. At higher rotational speeds, where acoustic modes changed to propagable cut-on condition, the results of both solvers differed significantly. The linearized solver was not capable of taking acoustic modes into account, which was done using the non-linear solver.

Terstegen et al. [3] and Sanders et al. [4] also highlighted the impact of acoustic modes on forced blade vibrations using the same compressor test rig as described in the present

work. Acoustic azimuthal modes were measured between the first rotor and the subsequent stator. In addition, blade tip-timing measurements were conducted and presented for the first rotor. These results were compared to numerical simulations using a linearized and a nonlinear frequency-based solver. Both solvers predicted excitation from the upstream inlet guide vane, while only the nonlinear solver was able to do so for the excitation from the downstream stator 1. The results showed that, if the rotor-stator-interaction of rotor 1 and its following stator row are neglected, this will lead to an underestimation of the blade-vibrational stresses of rotor 1 by up to 97% in their case.

An investigation of multistage effects was carried out, for example by Schrape et al. [5], who considered a 4.5-stage research compressor. By performing numerical simulations, Schrape et al. found that the interactions of rotor 1 with neighboring stator rows caused an additional excitation of different nodal diameters at rotor 2. These interactions were not present when rotor 1 was excluded in the numerical setup. When included, the excitation of different nodal diameters at the same frequency led to blade individual modal forcing. Similarly, Schoenenborn [6] showed blade individual aerodynamic excitation for a multi-row and multi-passage configuration by comparing a frequency-based to a time-resolved solver. Maroldt et al. [7] performed forced response simulations for a 2.5 stage axial compressor whilst taking acoustic modes and structural coupling of both rotors into consideration. They also found that acoustic modes play an important role in inter-stage coupling, while propagating from one stage to another.

In the context of axial turbines, Enghardt et al. [8] found frequencies originating from interactions between multiple rotors in a 3.5-stage axial turbine. The frequency with the fourth highest amplitude within the frequency spectrum, for example, was found to be an interaction between rotor 2 and rotor 3.

The results of this work showed that Tyler-Sofrin-Modes have an impact on forced blade vibrations, especially in the case of a blisk with a low structural damping. So far, most of the work on multistage effects has been done purely numerically or using measurements only up- and/or downstream of the blading for engine noise studies. The aim of the present work is to validate numerical simulation against experimental measurements of azimuthal mode analysis within a multistage axial compressor. For this purpose, numerical and experimental results of wall flush mounted pressure sensors in every axial gap throughout a 2.5-stage axial compressor are presented and discussed, together with an analysis of the measurement uncertainty.

2 METHODOLOGY

Hereinafter the basics of azimuthal mode analysis (AMA) will be presented, as well as the experimental and the numerical setup of the test case.

2.1 Azimuthal Mode Analysis

A periodic pressure field in a cylindrical duct can be described by an infinite sum of independent modes, as presented by Tyler and Sofrin [1]. These modes differ with frequency f , azimuthal mode order m , radial mode order n , flow conditions and channel geometry. Afterwards, a frame of reference with time t and cylindrical coordinates r , φ and x is used.

The decomposition of the time signal into its frequencies is performed using a Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT). The assignment of rotor of origin to the evaluated Engine Order (EO) and its frequency f can be made by

$$f = n_R \cdot EO = n_R \cdot \nu \cdot B \quad (1)$$

where n_R is the rotational speed of the rotor and B the number of rotor blades with its harmonics $\nu = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. For multiple rotors or stators (in a relative frame of reference) an extension can be made that is derived from [8] and given in Eq. 2.

$$\begin{aligned} f &= |n_R \cdot (\nu_1 B_1 \pm \nu_2 B_2 \pm \dots)| \\ &= |n_R \cdot (EO_{R1} \pm EO_{R2} \pm \dots)| \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

EO_{R1} and EO_{R2} are the EOs for rotor 1 and rotor 2 respectively. This extension, as presented here, is only valid for rotors with the same rotational speed, for example all on the same shaft. By examining Eq. 2, it is clear that a single frequency can have multiple sources. For the work presented here, it is assumed that a frequency originates from the lower harmonics (for example for EO70 the source is assumed as $1xEO32 + 1xEO38$, even though $20xEO32 - 15xEO38$ is also valid), since the lower harmonics of a single rotor are generally the more dominant frequencies.

For a given angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi f$, the pressure field $p_\omega(r, \varphi, x)$ can be described by Eq. 3, where upstream (-) and downstream (+) propagating waves are separated by different complex amplitudes $A_{m,n}^\pm$ and axial angular wavenumbers $k_{m,n}^\pm$.

$$p_\omega(r, \varphi, x) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(A_{m,n}^+ e^{ik_{m,n}^+ x} + A_{m,n}^- e^{ik_{m,n}^- x} \right) e^{im\varphi} f_{m,n}(r) \quad (3)$$

Here, $f_{m,n}(r)$ is the radial distribution, whose definition can be found in [9], for example. The radial mode orders n represent the number of zero crossings of a radial distribution, while the azimuthal mode order m is the number of maxima/minima in the circumferential direction defined by Tyler and Sofrin [1] as

$$m = \nu \cdot B + h \cdot V \quad (4)$$

with the number of stator vanes V and their harmonics $h = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$

Non-decaying mode propagation (Cut-On-Modes) is defined by the imaginary part of the axial angular wavenumber

$$k_{m,n}^\pm = \frac{k_m}{1 - M_x^2} (-M_x \pm \alpha_{m,n}) \quad (5)$$

with the Cut-On-Factor

$$\alpha_{m,n} = \sqrt{1 - (1 - M_x^2) \frac{\sigma_{m,n}^2}{(k_m R)^2}} \quad (6)$$

The axial angular wavenumber is complex if $\alpha_{m,n}$ is also complex. This depends on the axial Mach-number M_x , the eigenvalue of Bessel function $\sigma_{m,n}$ (for further information see [10], for example), and the angular wave number k_m , which is defined as

$$k_m = k - \frac{m\Omega}{c} \quad (7)$$

for a rigid body swirl, with free field angular wave number k and angular velocity Ω of angular flow speed. Subsequently, the Cut-Off condition is defined as

$$\Im(\alpha_{m,n}) \begin{cases} = 0 & \rightarrow \text{Cut-On} \\ \neq 0 & \rightarrow \text{Cut-Off} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Since only an azimuthal mode analysis was performed, no separation between upstream or downstream propagating modes can be made. Also, no radial distribution was measured or estimated. Therefore, Eq. 3 is split up and only Eq. 9 needs to be solved.

$$p_{\omega,r,x}(\varphi) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} A_m e^{im\varphi} \quad (9)$$

The complex azimuthal mode amplitudes A_m is the superimposition of all complex amplitudes $A_{m,n}^{\pm}$ of the same azimuthal mode order at a given radius and a given axial position. It has been calculated using the orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) algorithm [11]. Mode analysis using the OMP was presented by Behn et al. [12], for example, and was already validated by Terstegen et al. [3] on this rig before.

Throughout the presented work, the azimuthal modes will be written as m_{MO}^{EO} , with engine order EO and azimuthal mode order MO. As an example, the mode $m = -20$ at EO32 is written as m_{-20}^{32} .

2.2 Experimental Setup

Experimental investigations were conducted on the 2.5-stage axial compressor test rig at the institute. The rig is operated in cooperation with MTU Aero Engines and is equipped with a modern high aspect ratio blading that is derived from the front stages of an aero engine high pressure compressor [13]. Fig. 1 shows the cross-section of the blading section, including the measuring planes A-F & X and the blade counts. This closed-loop test rig is equipped with an air cooler and uses a throttle to adjust the operating point. For detailed information see [14], for example.

FIGURE 1: Blading section with measuring planes and blade counts

The highest possible rotational speed on the test rig is $n_{R,max} = 18000 \text{ min}^{-1}$, which corresponds to a frequency of $f = 300 \text{ Hz}$ for EO1. The measured operating points (OPs) are all on the working line of the compressor, which is shown in the compressor map in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2: Compressor map with operating points OP1-OP3

Unsteady pressure was recorded with probe-mounted Kulite XCE-062-SG sensors. The sensors are installed wall flush at the casing and can be interchanged between different sensor mountings in planes A-F & X. Planes A-F consist of at least five unevenly distributed sensor mountings each. Plane X has 12 almost equally spaced sensor mountings, covering a circumferential range of 127.8° . In total, 12 sensors were used for these planes, so that at least three separate measurements are necessary to obtain complete data for planes A-F of a single operating point.

To estimate the reproducibility and therefore the comparability of separate measurements, sensors from a preceding measurement campaign (also Kulite XCE-062-SG, referred to as “old” probes) were used. Due to a different probe design, old and new probes cannot be used in the respective other sensor mountings. The old probes are installed in three planes close to, but not identical to planes C (2 planes: C^- , C^{--}) and E (1 plane: E^-). These probes remain in the same sensor mountings for every measurement.

Data acquisition was done with a Müller BBM PAK MKII front end and WSB42X modules. The sampling rate was set to 204.8 kHz with a resolution of 16 bit. In addition to the pressure data, the data from a trigger sensor with one signal per revolution were also recorded to gain phase information in the post process.

The three stator rows (IGV, S1, S2) can be rotated independently to perform a virtual traversing of stationary sensors. Fig. 3 outlines the process of stator clocking for two consecutive circumferential positions.

FIGURE 3: Virtual clocking and phase correction

On the left-hand side of Fig. 3, a given base clocking of two stator rows is shown with a sensor mounted at the top position ($\varphi = 0^\circ$). Measurements in this position can be made without correction for the indicated sensor, since the absolute position (AP) and the desired position DP_1 are identical. The next position is indicated on the right-hand side. First, the rows are rotated in a way that the sensor on top has the same relative position to the stator vanes as the desired position DP_2 had when the stators were in base clocking. Since the trigger sensor is not rotated with the stator rows, a correction of phase information is necessary to obtain the same phase as in a case of a rotated sensor. For the azimuthal mode analysis, the phase information is necessary and therefore the measured complex amplitude p_{Meas} (result of the FFT) has to be corrected by Eq. 10, giving the corrected complex amplitude p_{Cor} .

$$p_{Cor} = p_{Meas} e^{i\omega\Delta t} \quad (10)$$

where the time difference Δt is calculated as

$$\Delta t = \frac{1}{n_R} \frac{\Delta\varphi_{Clocking}}{360^\circ} \quad (11)$$

The angle between the positions AP and DP_2 is denoted by $\Delta\varphi_{Clocking}$. If the phase information at different absolute sensor positions has to be compared, their absolute position must be taken into account in the same way.

The main measuring grid consists of 122 circumferential positions that were optimized by Terstegen et al. [3]. In addition, 5 circumferential positions were measured at the beginning and were repeated 4 times within the measuring process for the main grid. The data for these 5x5 additional measurements were used to evaluate the operating point stability within the uncertainty analysis. For every position, 10 s of raw pressure data were recorded and split to blocks of 10 revolutions before these data were ensemble-averaged in the post process.

2.3 Sensor calibration

All sensors used in this work were individually calibrated stationarily and dynamically. Stationary calibration was done to gain the voltage-pressure-relation for each sensor. Additional information from temperature variation and reproducibility measurements were used in a Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis.

For dynamic calibration, each sensor was calibrated against a GRAS 46BD-FV microphone within a rectangular channel, where both sensors (Kulite and microphone) were located directly opposite to each other, similar to the setup of Hurst et al. [15]. The calibration data have been post-processed by smoothing, diameter correction and shifting to the sensitivity of the stationary calibration for low frequencies. The diameter correction was carried out by an iterative 2D-approach for circular sensitive areas to eliminate the effect of pressure-averaging over sensitive areas of different diameter. The approach calculates the average pressure of a plane wave over the sensor surface for a given frequency and compares it to the respective pressure in the center of the sensor over a whole period of the plane wave. Time and space discretization are reduced until the change in amplitude gain and phase shift are lower than 0.1% over three consecutive iterations of increasing discretization. Compared to the 1D-approach of Hurst et al. [15] for rectangular sensitive areas, this approach shows, as expected, a smaller impact of averaging on the gain factor for a given sensitive area. In addition, the 2D-approach does not show any phase shift, as long as the wavelength is smaller than the sensor diameter.

Despite all sensors being of type Kulite XCE-062-SG, the new sensors for planes A-F & X are equipped with room temperature vulcanizing silicone around the sensitive area (referred to as RTV), which reduces the air volume behind the protective screen. A change in air volume results in altered eigenfrequency and gain factor, comparable to a Helmholtz resonator. The old

sensors for reproducibility measurements are not equipped with RTV. Further information on RTV and comparison of multiple sensors, both with and without RTV, were presented by Hurst et al. [15]. Post-processed calibration data for each sensor are shown in Fig. 4.

FIGURE 4: Post-processed dynamic calibration data for amplitude gain

The effect of the RTV can be seen clearly: the gain factor of the sensors with RTV is significantly lower than for the sensors without RTV at high frequencies. The sensors without RTV have a gain factor of 1.56 to 1.73 for highest calibration frequencies, while the ones with RTV have a gain factor of only 1.05 to 1.17 for those frequencies with an overall maximum of 1.20 within the calibration range. The sensors without RTV used in this work show a similar trend for the gain factor as presented by Hurst et al. for this type of sensor. For the sensors with RTV, no data for direct comparison were published, but the general difference for sensors with and without RTV is in agreement with the data presented by Hurst et al.

This outlines the importance of individual sensor calibration for this kind of sensors at high frequencies. Along with the gain, a frequency-dependent phase shift also occurs, which is of minor importance for this work and is therefore not presented here.

2.4 Uncertainty analysis

An uncertainty analysis was performed through a Monte Carlo simulation. The analysis uses experimental results from the azimuthal mode analysis, calculates time signals from these amplitudes and re-analyzes these signals, using the same evaluation as in the experimental post-process. Uncertainties are calculated by comparing the results with the given complex azimuthal mode amplitudes A_m in amplitude and phase. Fig. 5 illustrates the process for a single iteration.

Depending on the type, uncertainties were introduced at different points in the process chain. The different types of uncertainties are listed in Tab. 1 and marked with their corresponding symbols in Fig. 5.

All uncertainties of type “Sensor & measurement chain”, with the exception of the A/D conversion, are modeled through random distributions, partially superimposed with a pressure and

temperature dependency that was recorded along with stationary calibration data. Discretization was done, as in the experiment, with 16 Bit. The other two types of uncertainties are modeled through a random distributions without superimposition. Maximal manufacturing deviation of sensor mountings was assessed to be of 0.1° for the circumferential position. The deviation of phase and amplitude were calculated from the complex pressure $p_{\omega,r,x}(\varphi)$ of the 5x5 additional measuring positions of each sensor, which were recorded throughout the measuring process.

FIGURE 5: Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis - Process chain

TABLE 1: Uncertainty types in uncertainty analysis

● Manufacturing
Manufacturing deviation of sensor mountings in circumferential direction
■ Reproducibility
Deviation of phase and amplitude of remeasured positions
▲ Sensor & measurement chain
Zero drift of the sensor
Zero hysteresis of the sensor
Sensitivity drift of the sensor
Nonlinearity of voltage-pressure-relation
Random deviation of the sensor
Discretization (A/D conversion)

In total, 750 iterations of the process chain were carried out. It was found that this number is sufficient to obtain a result that is independent of the number of iterations. The deviation of azimuthal amplitude $|A_m|$ shown in the next sections, corresponds to the 95.4% range for positive and negative deviation, which is approximately the 2σ confidence interval in the case of a normal distribution.

2.5 Numerical Setup

Numerical simulations were performed using the flow solver TRACE (version 9.1), developed by the German Aerospace Center (DLR). Mesh resolution at solid walls was as follows: at hub and casing, an average y^+ of 3 and on the blades, an average y^+ of 1 was achieved. The simulation model consists of one blade per passage with a total mesh count of 12.0 to 12.8 million cells, depending on differing cell sizes near the wall for different operating points.

For the purpose of calculation the $k-\omega$ -turbulence model without transition model and a wall function for wall treatment was used. This setup has been validated by Sanders et al. [4] on this test rig before.

Inlet conditions and rotational speed are derived from experimental measurements, while the outlet static pressure was varied iteratively to match the same working line as the experimental results. To capture all experimental repetitions (three measurements per OP for complete data) of a single OP in one simulation, the experimental reference values were averaged over all three measurements before being used as boundary conditions.

Unsteady simulations were carried out by using the Harmonic Balance approach of TRACE [16]. Since not all modes could be simulated at once throughout the whole compressor, a separate simulation is set up for every azimuthal mode order. The domains of origin for each mode (e.g. rotor 1 and stator 1 for mode $m = -20 = 1xR1 - 1xS1$) were simulated using 5 harmonics. The propagating mode under consideration was simulated through all domains, as well as the stationary flow solution. As each mode had to be calculated in a separate simulation, only selected modes were simulated in order to limit the overall computational effort.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following sections, the analyzed data are presented, focusing on OP2. Due to the amount of data for multiple engine orders, axial planes and different sensors, only selected results representing most of the observed characteristics can be shown.

3.1 Frequency analysis

The most dominant EOs with large amplitudes $|p_\omega|$ have been evaluated by analysis of the frequency spectrum. By way of example, Fig. 6 shows the frequency spectrum of a single sensor in measurement plane E with dominant EOs highlighted. Their dedicated rotor can be determined on the basis of Fig. 7 (EO152 and EO190 are the fourth and fifth harmonic of rotor 2, but not shown in figure 7). Since every circumferential position has a different spectrum, the maximum of all 122 positions is shown for each frequency. In order to present a wide spectrum without the 20 kHz limitation from the dynamic calibration, all data in this section are shown without the correction with dynamic calibration data.

FIGURE 6: Frequency spectrum of a single sensor in plane E at OP2

As plane E is downstream of rotor 2, EOs resulting from each rotor can be found as dominant. In addition, EOs that are the result of an interaction of both rotors are also present. EO70, for example, is the result of this kind of interaction: $EO70 = 1xR1 + 1xR2$. The frequency analysis reveals that all dominant frequencies result from a single rotor or an interaction of both rotors. For a better identification of source rotor(s), the data will be presented in a different way. As such, Fig. 7 shows the engine orders that result from interaction of the first three harmonics of each rotor.

FIGURE 7: EOs for interactions of the first three harmonics of each rotor

Some engine orders are double, since frequencies are positive and therefore no difference between $EO6 = |1xR1 - 1xR2| = |1xR2 - 1xR1|$, for example, exists. For this reason, the lower bound of rotor 2 harmonics in these charts is set to zero. The bold numbers are the engine orders that are within the calibration range for every possible rotational speed of the test rig. The highest EO that is always within this range is EO66. Later on, EO70 will also be evaluated in the azimuthal mode analysis. This is done for OP2, where EO70 is within the range of calibration.

In Fig. 8, the results for the first five harmonics of both rotors in planes C and E at OP2 are depicted. Contrary to Fig. 6, the normalized maximum amplitudes of all sensors in the respective plane are indicated.

The prediction of individual mode propagation cannot be made using frequency spectra alone, but the presented data still indicates that propagation is mostly downstream for this compressor. The measuring planes upstream of stator 1 are dominated by rotor 1, while the planes downstream show dominant EOs of rotor 1, rotor 2 and also combinations of both. The behavior of OPs 1 and 3 is similar to this and so is not additionally shown here. It also turns out that for plane E, the amplitudes of the added EOs ($EO_{R1} + EO_{R2}$) tend to have higher amplitudes than the ones of the subtracted EOs ($EO_{R1} - EO_{R2}$). At this point, it should be noted that it is not possible to verify if this really is the case or if this is a result of a non-calibrated frequency range. Even though the sensors for planes A-F showed a relative low gain at 20 kHz, significantly higher frequencies were detected here.

FIGURE 8: Frequency spectrum of maximum normalized amplitudes $|p_\omega|$ for rotor harmonics at OP2

From the analysis of the frequency spectra, it can be deduced that frequencies resulting from interactions of several rotors can have amplitudes in the same order of magnitude as those resulting from a single rotor. These frequencies are also potential excitation sources for stators and rotors. Analogous to the investigations of Schrape et al. [5], modes with these frequencies may also excite blade vibration of additional nodal diameters at an up- or downstream rotor-row. Depending on whether the frequency decreases or increases due to the interaction of the rotor rows, it

is also possible that modes of such frequencies propagate either further or less far than modes of single rotor frequencies do.

3.2 Azimuthal mode analysis: Experimental analysis

Azimuthal mode analysis was performed for sensors in all 6 axial gaps, but was limited to the engine orders within the calibration range. Dynamic calibration had already been applied to all results presented below.

The following section presents selected azimuthal mode amplitudes $|A_m|$ at the casing for all OPs throughout the compressor. By way of example, a comparison of modes m_{-20}^{32} , m_{-14}^{38} and m_{+12}^{64} has been carried out. These modes each represent one of the modes with highest azimuthal mode amplitudes for their respective EOs. Fig. 9 shows these in measurement planes A to F. In this, and all following figures, the azimuthal mode amplitudes are normalized by the averaged amplitude of m_{-20}^{32} in plane E at OP3. The error bars represent the deviation between different sensors in the same measurement plane. The colored bar itself represents their arithmetic mean value for azimuthal mode amplitude. Since the reference value significantly exceeds the maximum value of most other modes shown, the y-axis was chosen individually for each plot. The estimated rows of origin of the analyzed modes according to Eq. 4 are shown in Tab. 2.

TABLE 2: Rows of origin for investigated mode orders

Mode	Rotor	Stator
m_{-20}^{32}	1xR1	-1xS1
m_{-8}^{32}	1xR1	-1xIGV
m_{-14}^{38}	1xR2	-1xS1
m_{+12}^{64}	2xR1	-1xS1
m_{+18}^{70}	1xR1+1xR2	-1xS1

The analyzed azimuthal mode amplitudes vary significantly with operating point, axial position and mode order. Even though amplitudes tend to increase with higher rotational speeds ($n_{R,OP1} < n_{R,OP2} < n_{R,OP3}$), no general determination for this can be made. The superimposition of different radial mode orders of the same azimuthal mode order changes according to the axial position and the operating point. Therefore, it is not possible to verify for which operating point the respective (radial) modes have the highest overall amplitudes, when taking into consideration the measured azimuthal mode amplitudes only.

The modes presented here, all propagate downstream, passing at least one blade row that is not part of their origin (see Tab. 2). In contrast, upstream propagation can only be observed for m_{+12}^{64} that is passing the IGV at OP1 and OP2. For azimuthal mode amplitudes, the possibility of destructive superimposition of different radial modes of the same azimuthal mode order in the respective measuring plane can not be excluded. Therefore, a low amplitude provides no proof, but indicates that m_{-20}^{32} and m_{-14}^{38} do not propagate upstream. The data are in agreement

with the analyzed frequency spectrum before: Modes propagate (mostly downstream) through the compressor while passing multiple blade rows and are therefore a possible source of blade vibration excitation at downstream blade rows.

FIGURE 9: Measured azimuthal mode amplitudes $|A_m|$ for selected modes of EO32, EO38 and EO64 throughout the compressor

The azimuthal mode analysis, based on individual sensors in the same measurement plane with different circumferential positions, shows large deviations in the amplitudes calculated. These deviations were also reported by Terstegen et al. [3] using the same test rig. The maximum deviation of more than 35%-points was observed for mode m_{-20}^{32} in plane F at OP2. This issue will be revisited in a later section of this paper.

A more detailed look into possible mode propagation was made by also taking the number of cut-on-modes into account. The analysis was done, for example, for the two modes m_{-20}^{32} and m_{+12}^{64} with and without observed upstream propagation respectively. The number of radial cut-on mode orders was calculated

using the approach presented in Eq. 6 and 8. In order to determine the Cut-On-Factor, differing inner and outer radii were taken into account, as well as the respective rotational speeds for OPs 1 to 3. Temperature, axial velocity and angular velocity were taken from the steady state CFD simulation of the respective OPs. The resulting number of cut-on modes is shown in Fig. 10.

At this point it should be noted that the circumferential velocity profile is not always in agreement with a solid body swirl. This assumption is valid downstream of the stator rows, but not downstream of the rotor rows. Taking a more complex angular velocity profile into account would also require a more complex approach to calculate the radial distribution of a mode and so for the Cut-On-Factor too. Enghardt et al. [17] did this, for example, by adopting a numerical approach.

FIGURE 10: Number of radial cut-on mode orders throughout the compressor for m_{-20}^{32} and m_{+12}^{64} at OP1, OP2 and OP3

For all analyzed modes, operating points, and axial planes in Fig. 10, at least one radial mode order is cut-on. There are actually more modes cut-on in the region upstream of rotor 1 than downstream of stator 2. A general cut-off condition between the blade rows is therefore not the reason for the absence of upstream propagation. The most likely reason for there being no propagation upstream of rotor 1 at OP3 is a supersonic region in the first rotor row covering part of the passage. However, this is not the case for OP1 and OP2, so even this region does not explain all the cases shown above, as m_{+12}^{64} proves. Therefore, the assumption is that reflections at the blades or cut-off condition within a blade row are the reasons for missing upstream mode propagation in the other cases.

3.3 Azimuthal mode analysis: Comparison of experimental and numerical results

Terstegen et al. [3] and Sanders et al. [4] focused on predicting aero-acoustic modes in the axial gap between rotor 1 and stator 1 and on the forced blade vibrations of rotor 1. Other axial planes were not further examined. In this present work, the analysis was extended to all axial gaps.

The comparison between simulation and measurement is made for the modes m_{-20}^{32} , m_{-8}^{32} and m_{+18}^{70} at OP2. The modes of EO32 are presented in Fig. 11. m_{-20}^{32} and m_{-8}^{32} both originate from rotor 1 and interact with the up- and downstream adjacent stator rows, respectively (see Tab. 2).

FIGURE 11: Azimuthal mode amplitudes $|A_m|$ for two modes of EO32 at OP 2

In most measurement planes, the numerically predicted azimuthal mode amplitudes at the casing are within or close to the scattering range of experimental evaluated sensors, as indicated by the error bars. Large deviations between numerical and experimental data were only observed in planes A and E for mode m_{-8}^{32} . This corresponds to the general behavior of all the modes which were simulated: a large part of the simulated azimuthal mode amplitudes lies in or close to the uncertainty range of the experiment. However, some simulated modes also show deviations from the experimental data at individual measurement planes.

So far, only results for single rotor frequencies are presented. As Fig. 8 implies, interaction frequencies of both rotors also occur in this compressor. EO70 was therefore selected for analysis because it is the most dominant EO of this type within the calibration range of the sensors. The results for m_{+18}^{70} at OP2 in Fig. 12 show qualitative agreement between simulation and measurement.

FIGURE 12: Azimuthal mode amplitudes $|A_m|$ for m_{+18}^{70} at OP 2

This implies that the harmonic balance approach is also able to predict the modes originating from more than one rotor and their propagation through the blade rows for the compressor investigated here.

For further comparison and evaluation, experimental uncertainties have to be analyzed and eliminated. A comprehensive validation of the numerical data would also require an experimental radial mode analysis. However, the axial gaps are too small for a wall-flush setup with multiple axially spaced sensors. This is especially true for the high number of radial cut on modes shown in Fig. 10.

3.4 Uncertainty analysis: Reproducibility

Due to the limited number of sensors, the data for one OP had to be acquired over three measurement days. Operational points therefore, had to be set up again and probes were switched from one sensor mounting to another. To verify the reproducibility, stationary data have been used, as well as AMA results for 12 additional sensors, which were mounted in axial planes C^- , C^{--} and E^- and remained fixed between the different measurements. Fig. 13 shows the result of one single sensor per plane for m_{-20}^{32} at OP2.

FIGURE 13: Reproducibility of m_{-20}^{32} at OP2 in planes C^- , C^{--} and E^- (one single sensor per plane is shown)

Sufficient reproducibility was achieved in the experiment to allow a qualitative comparison to numeric data. The largest deviation of azimuthal mode amplitude $|A_m|$ is less than 2.7%-points, which is far lower than the differences between sensors for most measurement planes and operation points. It must be mentioned however that in general, uncertainties increase for decreasing azimuthal mode amplitudes.

TABLE 3: Max. deviation to overall average of all three measurements of OP2

	Dev. -	Dev. +
n_R [$\frac{1}{\text{min}}$]	-5.2	+2.7
$p_{t,In}$ [Pa]	-28	+32
$T_{t,In}$ [K]	-0.30	+0.26
\dot{m} [$\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{s}}$]	-0.15	+0.17

In addition, Tab. 3 shows the lowest and highest values for rotational speed n_R , total inlet pressure $p_{t,In}$, total inlet temperature $T_{t,In}$ and mass flow \dot{m} as a deviation from the average values at OP2. As previously mentioned, the data were recorded over three measurement days. From this, it can be concluded that measurements on an OP spread over several days can be considered as a single measurement as far as qualitative comparison is concerned.

3.5 Uncertainty analysis: Circumferential inhomogeneity

Up until now, the deviation between sensors in the same axial plane has been presented as error bars of a joint average azimuthal mode amplitude $|A_m|$. Fig. 14 shows the individual azimuthal mode amplitudes of m_{-20}^{32} and m_{-14}^{38} for the five analyzed single sensors in plane D at OP2. The estimated single sensor uncertainties, which are the result of the Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis, are included as error bars.

FIGURE 14: Single sensor and average azimuthal mode amplitudes $|A_m|$ in Plane D at OP2

For both modes, large deviations are apparent between the sensors Se₁ to Se₅. For m_{-20}^{32} and m_{-14}^{38} the deviation between minimum and maximum values is 12.3%-points and 15.8%-points respectively. If these deviations are compared with the results from the Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis, it becomes clear that the uncertainties determined for each sensor are not large enough to explain the differences between the single sensors. For m_{-20}^{32} , the maximum single sensor uncertainty is 1.80%-points, while for m_{-14}^{38} it is only 0.75%-points. The analysis was performed separately for each sensor, which in turn led to individual results for the analysis. If both cases are analyzed in detail, it is noticeable that the error bars are not symmetrical around the determined value of the sensor. This can be attributed to the fact that not only symmetrical random variables are included in the calculations, but also pressure- and temperature-dependent variables. However, the uncertainties of the individual sensors determined here cannot explain the significant deviation between the sensors of the same measurement plane.

To assess the circumferential inhomogeneity, additional measurements were performed, followed by azimuthal mode analysis in plane X (positions X₁ to X₁₂) at OP2. In an initial measurement, all twelve sensors were used simultaneously. For a subsequent measurement on another day, each sensor was shifted two positions further into a different sensor mounting. For example, the sensor at position X₂ was shifted to position X₄. With this arrangement, the previous operating point was measured again. Fig. 15 shows the azimuthal mode amplitudes of m_{-20}^{32} for both measurements and their differences.

FIGURE 15: Single sensor azimuthal mode amplitudes $|A_m|$ for m_{-20}^{32} in Plane X at OP2

Fig. 15 (a) shows the azimuthal mode amplitudes for the reference measurement with the initial sensor arrangement. The highest amplitude of 74.9% at position X₆ exceeds the smallest of 33.5% at X₁₂ by more than a factor of 2.2. This is even more than the previously determined maximum deviation of about 35%-points. As already mentioned, none of the previously studied effects is sufficient to explain this large deviation. Fig. 15 (b) now shows the results of the repeat measurement with modified sensor arrangement. The pattern is exactly the same as in (a).

Finally, Fig. 15 (c) shows the difference between the two cases shown above. For the difference, the azimuthal mode amplitude at a point X_N of the second measurement (b) was subtracted from that of the first measurement (a). A maximum deviation of 3.6%-points was thus determined. This is still well below the deviations between the individual sensors. Among other things, this comparison includes the following sources of uncertainty:

- Re-setting the operation point
- Removing and re-installing the sensors
- Uncertainties of sensors and measurement chain

The investigations carried out so far have not been able to determine the cause of the significant differences between the sensors. With the findings to date, however, we assume that the cause lies within the main flow. For this reason, interfering influences, such as further instrumentation (e.g. leading edge measurement instrumentation) in the main flow, are being investigated in current numerical studies.

Regardless of the cause of the deviations, it is clear that measurements with few sensors or measurements that are limited to a small circumferential range should be interpreted with caution. Other measurements should always ensure that the range considered is representative for the investigation. The comparison of the measurements in different axial planes already shows that a low uncertainty of a considered mode order is not yet a guarantee for a low uncertainty of another mode order or for another operating point.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this work, the results of unsteady pressure measurements at the casing within the axial gaps of a 2.5-stage axial compressor have been presented. The evaluated experimental data have been compared with the solutions of numerical simulations using a frequency-based solver.

The frequency analysis of the experimental data have shown that not only the frequencies of the individual rotors and their harmonics have high amplitudes, but also those frequencies resulting from an interaction of both rotors. Acoustic modes at these frequencies can contribute to the excitation of forced blade vibrations, just as much as the frequencies of individual rotors can. As such, consideration should always be given to whether these frequencies also need to be taken into account.

The comparison of the results of the experimental azimuthal mode analysis with the simulation results has shown a qualitative agreement. A comprehensive validation of the numerical results was not possible due to the large deviation of the azimuthal mode amplitudes for different sensors in the same axial measurement plane, which were expected to be similar.

These deviations were further analyzed and it was shown that neither individual sensor errors, nor installation and removal of the sensors, nor insufficient reproducibility provide a sufficient explanation for these deviations. When measuring with a

small number of sensors or a locally limited measuring range, it should therefore always be ensured that the measurement results are representative for the investigation.

In current studies, various perturbations in the main flow, such as blade leading edge instrumentation, are being investigated with numerical simulations, to determine the cause of the deviations.

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NOMENCLATURE

$A_{m,n}$	Complex mode amplitude for mode m,n
A_m	Complex azimuthal mode amplitude for mode m
B	Number of rotor blades
c	Speed of sound
f	Frequency
$f_{m,n}$	Factor for radial distribution of a mode m,n
h	Harmonic of stator
k	Free field angular wave number
k_m	Corrected angular wave number for mode order m
$k_{m,n}$	Angular axial wave number for mode m,n
m	Azimuthal mode order
\dot{m}	Mass flow
M_x	Axial Mach number
n	Radial mode order
n_R	Rotational speed
p_t	Total pressure
p_ω	Complex pressure amplitude of angular frequency ω
r	Radial coordinate
R	Casing-radius
t	Time
T_t	Total temperature
v	Harmonic of rotor
V	Number of stator vanes
x	Axial coordinate
α	Cut-On-Factor
π_{tt}	Total to total pressure ratio
φ	Circumferential coordinate
σ	Eigenvalue of Bessel function
ω	Angular frequency
Ω	Angular velocity of rigid body swirl flow
\Im	Imaginary part of a complex number

Super- and Subscripts:

\square^+	Propagation in positive x-Direction
\square^-	Propagation in negative x-Direction
\square_{Cor}	Corrected value
\square_{In}	Value at the inlet
\square_m	Value for azimuthal mode order m
$\square_{m,n}$	Value for mode order combination m and n
\square_{Meas}	Measured value
\square_{Out}	Value at the outlet
\square_x	In axial direction
\square_ω	Value for constant angular frequency ω

Abbreviations:

AMA	Azimuthal Mode Analysis
AP	Absolute Position
DP	Desired Position
EO	Engine Order
FFT	Fast Fourier Transformation
IGV	Inlet Guide Vane
MO	Mode Order
OMP	Orthogonal Matching Pursuit
OP	Operational Point
R	Rotor
RTV	Room temperature vulcanizing silicon
S	Stator
Se	Sensor

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